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Color usage and citations in ADS/AIE-listed Orion-related graphics

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Introduction

Background. The Harvard-Smithsonian Center for Astrophysics manages the comprehensive paper database Astrophysics Data System (ADS), in collaboration with NASA. ADS hosts more than 13 million records, each bearing detailed citation and impact metrics, including total number of reads, citation count, h-indices, etc. ADS offers abstracts and links to the major astronomy and physics publications, both modern and increasingly historical contributions as well. ADS is also on the cutting edge of bibliometrics and information science related to the records they host,¹ maintaining rich records on citations, impact indices, networks, and more external resources. Moreover, especially helpful for this project is that a significant amount of this data is available through the ADS API,² of which this project has made significant use. Consequently, ADS provides a comprehensive, well-documented overview of the state of astronomy and astrophysics today.

The Astronomy Image Explorer is a database of images and figures published in American Astronomical Society journals, encompassing the following publications: The Astronomical Journal, The Astrophysical Journal, The Astrophysical Journal Letters, and The Astrophysical Journal Supplement. For the purposes of this project, AIE offers an almost-comprehensive database of graphics from the respective journals available on ADS; this project

¹ <https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/about/>

² <https://github.com/adsabs/adsabs-dev-api>

only analyzes relevant graphics available on AIE (a subset of the relevant graphics suggested by ADS). AIE, like ADS, subsequently offers a similar, if somewhat more restricted (to AAS publications) overview of astronomy but in graphical form. Combined, the resources of ADS and AIE can provide a preliminary toolkit for investigating the graphic and visual practices in astronomy and astrophysics, with aspirations to optimize data visualization especially for these fields.

Literature Review and Motivation. Astronomical and astrophysical visuals are distinct from other related disciplines in their frequent need to depict rich, multidimensional datasets concisely and comprehensibly. Especially within the last few decades, visualizations have come to rely on colors to depict multiple types or sets of data or even types of graphics. This practice has likely in part been aided by the advent of digital and online publication in the mid-1990s, greatly easing the ability to include complex (and often colorful) figures.³

Figure 1. Comparison of AIE graphics prior to 1995 (left) and present day (right). Anecdotally, we can observe the increased prevalence of color.

The efficacy of color has been a longstanding question particularly in the advertising and educational industries, especially with the advent of color television and other forms of projection. Numerous studies from the latter half of the last century began to systematically

³ From consultation with Albert Accomazzi and Edwin Henneken at ADS.

investigate a number of responses to color (compared to black and white), including preference, learning, emotional, and physiological responses. Winn and Everett concluded in 1979 that for primary and secondary school students, “color is an important cueing device [...] improv[ing] a learner’s ability to recall both relevant and irrelevant material.”⁴ They specifically used images and transparency slides, and found that “color is important to the meaning of a picture when it is a critical attribute of the pictured object or when attention is drawn to it.”⁵ Similarly, others have found that color is effective for so-called search tasks, such as locating points on maps, and perhaps is best employed “as an alerting function [...] as a means of stratifying a display.”⁶ Early educational studies indicated a preference for color but no significant benefit in learning. More specifically to informational colorful graphics, researchers found that “lettering is more legible with a neutral background” and that “color used in print examples will aid a student to focus on central information and reduce information processing time when used to complement externally paced oral instruction.”⁷

The latter described scenario — colorful graphics used in print to replace oral instruction — perhaps most closely resembles the function of graphics in scientific publications, of the studies conducted in advertising and educational studies. Other experiments are very much dependent on the particular contemporary technology they could employ or were concerned about, such as cathode ray tube TVs, transparencies, or other new modes of displaying colorful information. Thus, in addition to the fact that few studies of these kind exist today, even for our 21st century technologies, these early studies into the effects of color on learning and memory

⁴ Winn, William, and Richard J. Everett. "Affective Rating of Color and Black-and-White Pictures." *Educational Communication and Technology* 27, no. 2 (1979): 148-56. www.jstor.org/stable/30217989.

⁵ Winn et al. 1979.

⁶ Pett, Dennis, and Trudy Wilson. "Color Research and Its Application to the Design of Instructional Materials." *Educational Technology Research and Development* 44, no. 3 (1996): 19-35. www.jstor.org/stable/30221033.

⁷ Pett et al. 1996.

lack contemporary relevance for our digital age of scientific publication. Studying primary and secondary school education furthermore fails to account for the particularities of presenting data in academic papers in both audience and content conveyed. Many of the previously described studies (e.g. Winn et al. 1979) specifically studied the role of color in comprehending pictures of everyday objects, a type of graphic that rarely appears in academic scientific publications, especially astronomy, which rely more so on plots, graphs, maps, or images of unfamiliar “objects” in the sky. Moreover, the educational studies emphasize studying the effect of color on learning, which is a mode of graphic production and consumption that is distinct from the aims of comprehensiveness and comprehension of figures in scientific papers.

Consequently, this project seeks offer an initial exploration into color usage in data visualization, particularly for astronomy and astrophysics. Recommendations for effective data visualization exist,⁸ but it remains largely a realm for the individual proclivities and needs of projects and scientists. Analogous studies of color in graphics for in astronomy and astrophysics do not appear to be widely disseminated, if published at all, even though the needs of astronomical/astrophysical data visualization obviously necessitate vastly different practices than education, psychology, and advertising. This study seeks to undertake an exploratory, deliberate study into color data visualization practices with a long-view goal to uncover best color visualization practices as suits astronomical and astrophysical needs in particular.

Current study. The purpose of this study was to explore patterns of color usage in astronomical and astrophysical graphics and potentially its impact on comprehension, as very roughly approximated by number of refereed citations per year. This study compiled 4827 graphics from AIE and citation metrics from 1076 distinct bibliographic entries in ADS related to the search

⁸ Stone, Maureen, “Choosing Colors for Data Visualization,” January 2006.

term “Orion.” The graphics were evaluated on a “colorfulness” metric developed by Hasler and Süssstrunk 2003, and preliminary analysis into trends in visualization, color, and citation metrics were undertaken. This study offers a largely qualitative exploration into a somewhat handpicked selection of color and non-color visualizations in AIE. More rigorous quantitative, statistical analysis and more sophisticated metrics of “comprehension” will need to be developed to strengthen exploratory observations in this study, but this study seeks to establish first and foremost a potential, scalable procedure deliberately studying color in astronomical and astrophysical graphics.

Methods

Selecting the sample set. The Astronomy Image Explorer⁹ currently hosts over 700,000 graphics from across the American Astronomical Society publications, so a crucial step of this project was determining a representative but critical mass of graphics to assess. Graphics with color first appear on AIE in the mid-1990s,¹⁰ a trend likely reflective of the advent of electronic journal publishing, and the number of color graphics has only steadily increased (Fig. 1). Some of the earliest articles to employ color graphics were in the fields of stellar formation and related data-rich fields, such as Spaans et al. 1999.¹¹ Fig. 2 offers a rough portrait of increasing

⁹ <http://www.astroexplorer.org/>

¹⁰ <http://www.astroexplorer.org/search/eyJ0b1l1YXliOjE5OTUsInBhZ2UiOjEsInNob3ciOjI1fQ>

¹¹ <https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/1995ApJ...455L.167S>. “Photon Heating of Envelopes around Young Stellar Objects: an Explanation for CO J= 6—5,” *Astrophysical Journal Letters*, v. 455, p. L167

aggregate colorfulness in graphics from 1999 to 2017 compared to number of graphics from the same period (see following subsection for explanation of the years of 2005, 2007, 2008).

Figure 2a,b. Number of graphics from 1999–2017, and aggregate “colorfulness” of all graphics in each year, 1999–2017.¹²

¹² Comments received on the draft suggested depicting this time growth of colorfulness as a violin plot; however, due to time constraints and lack of experience with the necessary software, that more concise plot will be reserved for continuing work on this study.

Subsequently, we chose to limit the sample for current study to the ADS search term “Orion,” aiming to study graphics from articles related to the nebula and star-forming region, since these appeared to be the subdisciplines most in need of color data visualization. Orion references the Orion Nebula, a common object of study for stellar and galactic formation. The ADS search entered was thus: “bibstem:(ApJ OR ApJL OR ApJS OR AJ) year:1997-2019 Orion,” where the so-called bibstems ApJ, ApJL, ApJS, and AJ limit the search to AAS publications.¹³ This returns 1303 ADS bibliographic records.¹⁴

Assembling citation metrics and graphics. All data and graphics for this project were assembled from ADS’s publicly available API, including citation metrics, impact indices, etc. With generous Python assistance from ADS’s Edwin Henneken, a set of citation metrics and graphics were retrieved from this API for each year (see Appendix B for script). A similar process was used to retrieve the set of graphics of interest. Citation metrics (total citations, normalized citations, refereed citations, normalized citations, total reads, total downloads) are retrievable from the ADS API.¹⁵ This study largely employed the refereed citation metric, normalized for age by dividing by the age of the article to acquire an estimate of number of refereed citations per year. Metrics retrieval was initially intended to be carried out for the 1303 records in the range of years selected in the aforementioned ADS search (1997-2019), but for still unclear reasons, metrics and graphics are currently not retrievable for the following years: 1997, 1998, 2007, 2008, 2018, 2019. Graphics from the years of 2005 and 2014 likely also suffer from this same unknown obstacle, though a small set (10 and 39 graphics, respectively) could

¹³ ADS catalogs more than just the AAS publications, but AIE only stores graphics from AAS publications, so this limitation was necessary to ensure all articles would have associated high-resolution graphics.

¹⁴[https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/search/q=bibstem%3A\(ApJ%20OR%20ApJL%20OR%20ApJS%20OR%20AJ\)%20year%3A1997-2019%20Orion&sort=date%20desc%2C%20bibcode%20desc&p=0](https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/search/q=bibstem%3A(ApJ%20OR%20ApJL%20OR%20ApJS%20OR%20AJ)%20year%3A1997-2019%20Orion&sort=date%20desc%2C%20bibcode%20desc&p=0)

¹⁵ https://github.com/adsabs/adsabs-dev-api/blob/master/Metrics_API.ipynb

still able to be assembled. The set of graphics from 2015 is likely also an incomplete set, as a number of graphics were duplicated during the retrieval process. Thus, the set of graphics represented in this paper is more closely characterized as graphics from Orion-related AAS publications between the years of 1999 and 2017. Though this set is not even a comprehensive graphical portrait of these years, the retrieval process returns 4827 graphics, which we believe is a sufficient mass for the early stages of this study.

Measuring color. Two methods of measuring color were undertaken in this study: for current purposes, we will refer to them as RGB fraction and colorfulness.

RGB fraction. With the generous assistance of Catherine Zucker, we initially attempted to categorize each pixel in each graphic with a primary (red, green, blue), secondary (orange, purple, yellow), black, or white color. This is done by calculating the distance from any given RGB value of a pixel to the nearest RGB value of either a primary, secondary color, black, or white. The total number of pixels of each color is then presented as a fraction out of the total number of pixels in the entire graphic. This method also included very basically evaluating whether a graphic was color or “grayscale,” i.e. only contains black and white pixels.

This method, however, has questionable fidelity to how a graphic appears visually, particularly by inadequately characterizing gray pixels. Gray has RGB values of (128, 128, 128), on average, which is almost equidistant to every color but fractionally closer to orange and purple. A sizeable number of graphics are grayscale, so this misidentification would significantly misrepresent the use of color. This also renders most of the secondary color assignments from this method unreliable, but primary color fractions (RGB) are still reliable and used lightly in the analysis of this project.

Colorfulness. Instead, we employed the “colourfulness metric” described by Hasler and Ssstrunk 2003.¹⁶ Specifically, we rely on their efficient metric described in Section 7, which employs the standard deviations and means among opponent color spaces. Broadly, if an image is separated into its R, G, and B channels:

$$rg = R - G$$

$$yb = \frac{1}{2}(R + G) - B$$

The standard deviations σ_{rg} and σ_{yb} are then computed, as are the means μ_{rg} and μ_{yb} . The colorfulness metric C is then a linear combination of the overall standard deviation and mean:

$$\sigma_{rgyb} = \sqrt{\sigma_{rg}^2 + \sigma_{yb}^2}$$

$$\mu_{rgyb} = \sqrt{\mu_{rg}^2 + \mu_{yb}^2}$$

$$C = \sigma_{rgyb} + 0.3\mu_{rgyb}$$

In short, this returns a color metric C that is an ascending scale describing the degree of colorfulness of an image. That is, $C = 0$ is an image of no color, while above $C = 75$ is rather colorful (Fig. 2). Calculating this metric can furthermore be scripted into Python with the aid of OpenCV, and the assistance of Catherine Zucker.¹⁷ This colorfulness metric was subsequently

¹⁶ Hasler, David, Sabine Ssstrunk. “Measuring colourfulness in natural images,” <https://infoscience.epfl.ch/record/33994/files/HaslerS03.pdf>.

¹⁷ <https://www.pyimagesearch.com/2017/06/05/computing-image-colorfulness-with-opencv-and-python/>

calculated for each available graphic and constitutes the primary metric for the bulk of this analysis.

Figure 3. Hasler and Süssstrunk’s colorfulness metric, computed and arranged in a montage with OpenCV and Python. Figure credit: <https://www.pyimagesearch.com/2017/06/05/computing-image-colorfulness-with-opencv-and-python/>

Examining highly cited graphics. This study qualitatively examined the most highly cited graphics in the sample, defined as greater than ten refereed citations per year. We developed 33 “types” of graphics, including different formats (e.g. image, plot, map), data sources (e.g. simulation), and features of the graphics (e.g. legend, annotations, error bars).¹⁸ Each highly cited graphic ($n = 466$) was categorized among these types of graphics. We then qualitatively examined four different populations within this categorized, highly cited subset: few types of graphics and high colorfulness; many types of graphics and high colorfulness; few types of graphics and low colorfulness; many types of graphics and low colorfulness. We also tentatively begin to look for trends, though without full-fledged statistical analysis.

¹⁸ The full list can be found at this Google Form: <https://forms.gle/VJFmfYtqDpQxqoMAA>.

Results

Colorfulness and citations. Broadly, there does not appear to be a strong correlation between colorfulness and refereed citations; however, the most highly cited graphics are frequently also the most colorful. The average colorfulness metric of all 4827 graphics was 12.9, which would appear as a somewhat more than grayscale image; the median was 0 (a completely colorless image). As Fig. 4 demonstrates, colorfulness of the graphics generally was from $C = 0$ –10 and from $C \approx 15$ –75 (somewhat colorful). About 240 graphics have $C > 75$, or very colorful; graphics of almost no color are far more prevalent.

Figure 4. Age-normalized refereed citations vs. colorfulness metric. Highlighted points indicate greater than 10 citations per year, defined as highly cited in this study ($n = 466$).

Most highly cited graphics. 466 graphics were cited greater than 10 times per year and were subsequently categorized according to type of graphic previously described. Fig. 5 shows the frequency of “formats” of graphic (e.g. plot, image, or map, etc.); Fig. 6 shows the frequency of certain “features” of graphic (e.g. legend, error bar, etc.).

Figure 5. Frequency of types of format of highly cited graphics.

Figure 6. Frequency of types of features of highly cited graphics.

Within the highly cited population of the graphics, no clear correlation between total number of types of graphic and age-normalized citations (Fig. 7) appears to emerge. That is, the

more categories of graphics that any one graphic falls in does not appear to be correlated with the number of refereed citations per year for that same graphic.

A clear correlation between types of graphic and colorfulness also does not appear to exist based on the current sample; however, highly cited graphics appear to be generally $C < 50$ and between 3 to 5 categories of graphic applicable to any one graphic (Fig. 8).

Figure 7. Total types of graphic and age-normalized referee citations; no clear correlation.

Figure 8. Total types of graphic and colorfulness of highly cited graphics.

The potential correlation between citations and colorfulness appears somewhat more likely within this subset of highly cited graphics (Fig. 9), though a linear trendline does not describe this sample particularly well, which had three unusually highly cited bibliographic entries (age-normalized citations > 20 per year).

Figure 9. Age-normalized refereed citations and colorfulness. A potential correlation potentially may exist for citations < 20 per year.

Populations of highly cited graphics. On average, the highly cited graphics subset had 3.8 different types of graphic for each graphic (maximum 8). From Fig. 8, we then qualitatively sampled the “extremes” of this subset for the four populations within the subset described in Table 1 for particular bibliographic entries. (Future larger-scale samples would become even more granular, i.e. more cells in the table.) See Appendix B (or ADS/AIE) for a sample of graphics from these populations. Even these very broadly categorized populations, however, offer an interesting portrait of the usage of color and types of colorful graphics in astronomical

and astrophysical papers; for example, the least number of types of graphics and least colorful graphics are retrieved from a 1999 paper (1999ApJ...525..772P), all with the same “format” of graphic, some type of line plot. The most colorful and most types of graphics are retrieved from a 2017 paper (2017ApJ...843..63F) that employs both greyscale, rudimentary line plots and also highly complex, multipane graphics with multiple formats and types overlaid within one graphic.

<p>few types of graphics, high C</p> <p>e.g. 2017ApJ...846..122P average 3.69 types of graphics average $C = 50.81$</p>	<p>many types of graphics, high C</p> <p>e.g. 2017ApJ...843..63F average 5.86 types of graphics average $C = 34.01$</p>
<p>few types of graphics, low C</p> <p>e.g. 1999ApJ...525..772P average 1.88 types of graphics average $C = 0$</p>	<p>many types of graphics, low C</p> <p>e.g. 2012AJ...144..192M average 4.79 types of graphics average $C = 23.05$</p>

Table 1. Populations of types of graphic and colorfulness with highly cited graphics.

Discussion and Conclusions

This project constitutes, we think, a preliminary excursion into a topic of significance within data visualization communities. Here, we attempt to preliminarily trace out potential relationships between color and comprehensibility, as measured by citation metrics, within the disciplines of stellar and galactic formation (“Orion”-related records). Though this project currently does not find any strict correlation between color usage and frequency of citation, it does begin to systematically characterize usage of color in the astronomical and astrophysical disciplines. More complex types of graphics (i.e. a graphic qualifying for numerous “types” of graphic) have, even from just qualitative observation and analysis, become much more prevalent. Within the highly cited subset of graphics, there may be a correlation between these visualization practices and comprehensibility, as potentially gestured by Fig. 8, though more refined metrics of

comprehensibility than refereed citations will need to be developed to strengthen this observation.

This project also selected as an initial, representative set the records that appear in the ADS search “Orion,” to gauge the fields of stellar and galactic formation that were among the first to introduce into their graphics. These are, obviously, not the only subsets of the astronomical and astrophysical communities that employ color in graphics; future iterations of this project could expand into these alternate fields or formulate sensitive ways of accounting for disciplinary practices and needs. A larger sample could potentially also allow for stronger evidence of correlations or trends. This would also allow for more rigorous quantitative analysis, rather than strictly the qualitative overview offered in this study.

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Appendix A: Code

Both of the following codes were run for each year assessed in this project (courtesy of Edwin Henneken):

```
get_metrics_v3.py
```

```
import os
import sys
import csv
import urllib.request, urllib.error, urllib.parse
import json

api_token = 'xxx'
metrics_url = 'https://api.adsabs.harvard.edu/v1/metrics/%s'

try:
    bibcodes_file = sys.argv[1]
except:
    sys.exit('Please provide name of file containing bibcodes')

results_file = "%s.metrics.csv" % bibcodes_file.split('.')[0]
output = open(results_file, "w")
# write header to output file
output.write("bibcode", "total citations", "normalized citations", "refereed
citations", "normalized refereed citations", "total reads", "total downloads\n")
with open(bibcodes_file) as csvfile:
    reader = csv.reader(csvfile, delimiter=',')
    for row in reader:
        bibcode = row[0].strip()
```

```

# Check if we have a valid bibcode (has to be 19 characters long)
if len(bibcode) != 19:
    continue

url = metrics_url % bibcode
req = urllib.request.Request(url)
req.add_header('Content-type', 'application/json')
req.add_header('Accept', 'text/plain')
req.add_header('Authorization', 'Bearer %s' % api_token)
resp = urllib.request.urlopen(req)
data = json.load(resp)

# citation statistics
total_cits = data['citation stats']['total number of citations']
norm_cits = data['citation stats']['normalized number of citations']
ref_cits = data['citation stats']['total number of refereed citations']
norm_ref_cits = data['citation stats']['normalized number of refereed citations']

# usage statistics
total_reads = data['basic stats']['total number of reads']
total_downl = data['basic stats']['total number of downloads']

output.write("%s", %s, %.2f, %s, %.2f, %s, %s\n" % (bibcode, total_cits, norm_cits,
ref_cits, norm_ref_cits, total_reads, total_downl))

output.close()

get_graphics_v3.py

import os
import sys
import csv

```

```
import urllib.request, urllib.error, urllib.parse
import json
from time import sleep
from random import random

api_token = 'xxx'
graphics_url = 'https://api.adsabs.harvard.edu/v1/graphics/%s'

# Run the script like: if you have a file with bibcodes, one per line, called orion_1997.txt
# python get_graphics orion_1997.txt
try:
    bibcodes_file = sys.argv[1]
except:
    sys.exit('Please provide name of file containing bibcodes')

# The output CSV file will be named by replacing the extension of the input file by
".graphics.csv"
results_file = "%s.graphics.csv" % bibcodes_file.split('.')[0]
output = open(results_file, "w")
# The downloaded images will be stored in a subfolder of the "images" directory.
# This subfolder is named using the file name of the input file
image_dir = 'images/%s' % bibcodes_file.split('.')[0]
# check if we have a subdirectory 'images'
if not os.path.exists('images'):
    os.mkdir('images')
# Create the subfolder, if it doesn't exist already
```

```

if not os.path.exists(image_dir):
    os.mkdir(image_dir)
# Write header to output file
output.write("bibcode","image id","image URL","image file"\n)
with open(bibcodes_file) as csvfile:
    reader = csv.reader(csvfile, delimiter=',')
    for row in reader:
        # Every row should consist of just one bibcode
        # We will retrieve graphics information from the API. For example
        # https://api.adsabs.harvard.edu/v1/graphics/2015ApJS..216...18N
        bibcode = row[0].strip()
        # Check if we have a valid bibcode (has to be 19 characters long)
        if len(bibcode) != 19:
            continue
        url = graphics_url % bibcode
        req = urllib.request.Request(url)
        # We need to add our API token to the request
        req.add_header('Content-type', 'application/json')
        req.add_header('Accept', 'text/plain')
        req.add_header('Authorization', 'Bearer %s' % api_token)
        # Now we can do the API request
        resp = urllib.request.urlopen(req)
        # The API sends back data in JSON format
        data = json.load(resp)
        # Cycle through all the figures for the paper corresponding with the current bibcode
        for figure in data['figures']:
            figure_id = figure['figure_id']

```

```

# We grab the thumbnail URL to guess the highres image URL
thumbnail_url = figure['images'][0]['thumbnail']
# Guess highres image URL
highres_url = thumbnail_url.replace('_tb','_hr')
# Define the file name for the highres image
highres_file= "%s/%s" % (image_dir, os.path.basename(highres_url))
# If this file does not yet exist, download it
if not os.path.exists(highres_file):
    # Do a HEAD request to check if the guessed URL actually exists
    request = urllib.request.Request(highres_url)
    request.get_method = lambda : 'HEAD'
    response = urllib.request.urlopen(request)
    if response.code == 200:
        # The HEAD request indicates that this is a valid URL, so we can download
the image
#         filedata = urllib2.urlopen(highres_url)
        request = urllib.request.Request(highres_url)
        filedata = urllib.request.urlopen(request)
        datatowrite = filedata.read()
        # Write the image data to file
        with open(highres_file, 'wb') as f:
            f.write(datatowrite)
# Write image data to the output CSV file
if os.path.exists(highres_file):
output.write("%s", "%s", "%s", "%s\n"%(bibcode,figure_id,highres_url,highres_file))
else:

```

```
    output.write("%s", "%s", "%s\n"%(bibcode, figure_id, "NA", "NA"))
    sleep(random())
# Close the output file
output.close()
```

Appendix B: Selected Sample Graphics

1999ApJ...525..772P (Palla, Francesco and Steven W. Stahler, "Star Formation in the Orion Nebula Cluster," *The Astrophysical Journal*, 525(2):772–783.)

2012AJ...144..192M (Megeath, S.T., et al., “The Spitzer Space Telescope Survey of the Orion A and B Molecular Clouds. I. A Census of Dusty Young Stellar Objects and a Study of Their Mid-infrared Variability,” *The Astronomical Journal*, 144(6), 27 pp., 2012.)

2017ApJ...846..122P (Pattle, et al., "The JCMT BISTRO Survey: The Magnetic Field Strength in the Orion A Filament," *The Astrophysical Journal*, 846(2), 21 pp.)

2017ApJ...843..63F (Kirk, H., et al., “VizieR Online Data Catalog: Virial analysis of the dense cores in Orion A,” *The Astrophysical Journal*, 2017.)

